

The Analysis of Job Satisfaction and Employee Experience on Turnover Intention in Telecommunication Service Companies

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ABSTRACT: Employee turnover is a rising issue in Indonesia's information and communication sector. PT XYZ reported a turnover rate of 17.2% in 2024. This study investigates the influence of job satisfaction and employee experience on turnover intention among PT XYZ's permanent employees. Grounded in Job Characteristics Model (Hackman & Oldham, 1976), Organizational Commitment Theory (Allen & Meyer, 2000), and Turnover Process Theory (Mobley, 1977), this research uses a quantitative method involving 45 respondents. Descriptive statistics show both job satisfaction (mean = 3.24) and employee experience (mean = 2.53) at "Fair" levels. Turnover intention also scored "Fair" (mean = 2.14), signaling moderate retention risks. Pearson correlation shows significant negative relationships between job satisfaction ($r = -0.482$), employee experience ($r = -0.404$), and turnover intention. Multiple linear regression reveals job satisfaction as a marginally significant predictor of turnover intention ($B = -0.480$, $p = 0.059$), while employee experience has no significant effect. The study proposes data-driven solutions including improvements in compensation, career growth, recognition, and conflict resolution. Findings offer practical insight into PT XYZ and support future research on turnover dynamics.

KEYWORDS: Employee experience, job satisfaction, retention, HR strategy, turnover intention.

INTRODUCTION

The Information and Communication industry in Indonesia has demonstrated significant growth over the past decade, as illustrated in the graph below (DataIndustri Research, n.d.). Based on data from the Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) and Bank Indonesia (BI), the industry's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) contribution has increased steadily from IDR 256.048 trillion in 2010 to an estimated IDR 645.629 trillion in 2024. Despite slight fluctuations, the annual growth rate remains robust, with a peak of 12.28% in 2012 and consistent growth rates above 7% in recent years.

This growth reflects the critical role of the Information and Communication sector in driving Indonesia's economic development. Companies within this industry, such as PT. XYZ, are integral to supporting this expansion through technological innovation and service delivery. However, rapid growth also presents challenges, including heightened competition, increasing client demands, and workforce management complexities.

For PT. XYZ, employee turnover has become a pressing issue in recent years. While the company strives to maintain its reputation as a solution-driven provider, high turnover rates have introduced significant operational inefficiencies and financial burdens. One major consequence is the escalating cost of training and certifying newly recruited employees, who are needed to replace those who have resigned. This not only strains the company's budget but also disrupts workflow and impacts the quality of services delivered to clients.

Given the growing importance of retaining a skilled and engaged workforce to meet the demands of the expanding industry, it is crucial to explore the factors influencing employee turnover. This study aims to investigate the relationship between employee satisfaction, engagement, and turnover intention, providing actionable insights to address this critical business challenge.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides the conceptual foundation for the study. It defines and elaborates on the three main variables: job satisfaction, employee experience, and turnover intention. Each variable is examined in terms of its definition, contributing factors, and impact on organizational outcomes.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to the emotional and evaluative response employees have toward their work. Locke (1976) defines it as a pleasurable emotional state from job appraisal, while Spector (1997) views it as the degree of liking or disliking one's job, encompassing both affective and cognitive aspects. Weiss (2002) emphasizes that job satisfaction is a collection of attitudes toward various job elements, and Luthans (2011) adds that it stems from how well job outcomes meet expectations. These perspectives collectively frame job satisfaction as a multidimensional construct shaped by experience, emotion, and evaluation.

A meta-analysis by Hapsari et al. (2023) identifies five key factors influencing job satisfaction across sectors: respectful treatment, fair compensation, trust in leadership, job security, and opportunities to use one's skills. These dimensions, reflected in this study's framework, significantly affect how employees perceive their roles and contribute to satisfaction levels.

Job satisfaction brings tangible organizational benefits. According to Judge et al. (2001), satisfied employees are more productive, committed, and deliver better service, which enhances performance and customer satisfaction. Moreover, satisfaction lowers turnover and absenteeism while promoting organizational citizenship behavior. Conversely, Spector (1997) links low satisfaction to absenteeism, withdrawal, and counterproductive behaviors, which can harm company outcomes. Therefore, fostering job satisfaction is crucial to sustaining employee engagement and organizational health.

Employee Experience

Employee experience (EX) refers to how employees perceive and interact with their workplace throughout their journey in the organization. Plaskoff (2017) describes it as a strategic HR approach aligning the work environment with employees' needs, while Morgan (2017) defines it as the totality of interactions shaped by culture, technology, and physical space. These views emphasize that EX is holistic, integrating emotional, social, and organizational factors that influence engagement and retention.

Aurel & Febriansyah (2024) found that EX dimensions such as leadership, meaningful work, and work-life balance significantly impact turnover intention in fast-paced organizational settings. Their findings underscore the strategic role of EX in reducing attrition.

Drawing from Plaskoff and Morgan, this study categorizes EX into three core domains: social experience (e.g., support from leaders and peers), work experience (e.g., clarity, autonomy, recognition), and organizational experience (e.g., mission alignment, technological access, and workplace environment). These are translated into five measurable dimensions: social environment, work design, organizational culture, technological support, and physical workspace. Each plays a crucial role in shaping how employees feel, perform, and stay with the organization.

Positive EX is linked to multiple organizational benefits. It enhances engagement, productivity, collaboration, and strengthens employer branding. Employees who feel supported are more adaptive to change and committed to long-term growth. Conversely, poor EX leads to disengagement, misalignment with company values, and ultimately, higher turnover risk. Therefore, investing in employee experience is essential for building a resilient, high-performing workforce.

Turnover Intention

Turnover intention refers to an employee's conscious plan to leave their organization voluntarily. Mobley (1977) identifies it as the immediate precursor to actual resignation, while Griffeth and Horn (2001) define it as the perceived likelihood of quitting within a set period. Allen et al. (2005) emphasize that it reflects an employee's attitude toward leaving, shaped by job satisfaction, organizational context, and personal circumstances.

As a leading predictor of actual turnover, turnover intention is widely used in studies on employee behavior and HR strategy.

High turnover intention can severely disrupt organizational performance. According to Allen et al. (2010), it leads to increased recruitment and training costs, productivity loss from role gaps, and even legal expenses in certain cases. It also impacts team morale and weakens customer satisfaction due to unstable service quality. Reducing turnover intention is therefore essential to maintaining workforce continuity and protecting operational efficiency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts a two-phase mixed-method research design to provide both contextual depth and empirical validation. In the first phase, an exploratory interview was conducted with the HR Manager of PT XYZ to uncover underlying issues contributing to the

increasing employee turnover rate. The HR Manager identified low job satisfaction and poor employee experience, especially among employees under 30, as possible causes. These insights guided the formulation of the research variables.

The second phase involved a quantitative survey using a structured questionnaire to measure job satisfaction, employee experience, and turnover intention among permanent employees. This approach enabled the statistical validation of relationships hypothesized in the initial phase.

A quantitative research approach was chosen due to its strength in measuring and analyzing relationships between variables. The design includes both descriptive and correlational components. Descriptive research addresses the first research question (RQ1) by summarizing the levels of job satisfaction and employee experience using mean scores and standard deviations. Correlational research addresses the second research question (RQ2) by examining the strength and direction of the relationships among the variables, without implying causality.

The study focuses exclusively on permanent employees of PT XYZ to ensure that the findings are relevant to long-term human resource strategies and are not affected by differing contractual conditions associated with temporary or outsourced staff.

Data Collection Method

Data for this study were collected through two complementary methods: interviews and questionnaires. The exploratory interview with the HR Manager provided qualitative insights that shaped the questionnaire content. It helped identify key concerns related to employee turnover, job satisfaction, and experience.

The primary method for collecting empirical data was a structured questionnaire distributed to permanent employees. The questionnaire included items specifically designed to measure the constructs of job satisfaction, employee experience, and turnover intention. All items were rated using a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). This format, as suggested by Arikunto (2010), omits a neutral midpoint to minimize central tendency bias and elicit more decisive responses.

Data Collection Method

The analysis of data was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics and is organized into two main parts: descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive analysis was used to address RQ1 by calculating mean scores and interpreting them based on Sugiyono's (2017) classification scale. The interpretation scale categorizes scores as follows:

Table 1. Interpretation Scale

Average Score	Category
1.00 – 1.75	Very Poor
1.76 – 2.50	Poor
2.51 – 3.25	Fair
3.26 – 4.00	Good

This approach enabled a clear and concise evaluation of employee perceptions.

Inferential statistics were used to address RQ2. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied to determine the strength and direction of the relationships among job satisfaction, employee experience, and turnover intention. Correlation values range from -1 to +1, with negative values indicating inverse relationships, positive values indicating direct relationships, and values near zero suggesting weak or no linear correlation.

To further analyze the predictors of turnover intention, multiple linear regression was performed using the following model:

$$\text{Turnover Intention} = \beta^0 + \beta^1 (\text{Job Satisfaction}) + \beta^2 (\text{Employee Experience}) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- β^0 = constant
- β^1, β^2 = regression coefficients
- ε = error term

Prior to interpreting the regression output, assumption testing was conducted to ensure the validity of the model. These assumptions include linearity (verified through scatterplots), normality (checked using histograms and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test),

homoscedasticity (assessed via residual plots), independence of residuals (tested using the Durbin-Watson statistic), and multicollinearity (evaluated using the Variance Inflation Factor, with a threshold of VIF < 5).

Hypothesis testing was performed with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates statistical significance. Additionally, the R^2 value was used to evaluate the model's explanatory power, while the β coefficients were analyzed to determine the relative strength and direction of each predictor.

This comprehensive methodological framework ensures the reliability and validity of the study findings, providing a solid foundation for making informed recommendations to PT XYZ regarding strategies to improve employee retention.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Respondents

A total of 45 permanent employees participated in the survey, representing a significant portion of PT. XYZ's core workforce. The demographic breakdown of the respondents is crucial for understanding the representativeness of the sample.

Table 2. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Category	Sub-Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	32	71.11%
	Female	13	28.89%
Age	21 -25	7	15.56%
	26 - 30	5	11.11%
	31 - 35	8	17.78%
	36 - 40	8	17.78%
	>40	17	37.78%
Education	SMA/SMK	13	28.89%
	D1	1	2.22%
	D3/S1	28	62.22%
	S2	3	6.67%
Tenure	<1 year	1	2.22%
	1 - 5 years	16	35.56%
	>5 - 10 years	6	13.33%
	>10 years	22	48.89%

The demographic profile indicates a workforce predominantly composed of male employees (71.11%), with the largest segment falling within the >40 years age group (37.78%). Most employees (62.22%) hold a D3/S1 education, and the majority have worked at PT. XYZ for more than 10 years (48.89%), suggesting a relatively experienced and stable workforce. Meanwhile, 35.56% have been working for 1–5 years, indicating a mix of long-term and mid-level tenure employees.

Validity Test

To ensure the questionnaire accurately measured the intended constructs, a validity test was conducted using Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC). With 45 respondents and a significance level of 0.05, the critical r value is 0.294. All items for job satisfaction (25 items), employee experience (15 items), and turnover intention (3 items) exceeded this threshold, confirming 100% validity. These results support the inclusion of all items in subsequent reliability and inferential analysis.

Table 3. Item Validity

Dimension	Item	r-Count	r-Table	Verdict
Respectful treatment of all employees at all levels	JS1_1	0.397	0.294	Valid
	JS1_2	0.454	0.294	Valid
	JS1_3	0.466	0.294	Valid

	JS1_4	0.414	0.294	Valid
	JS1_5	0.502	0.294	Valid
Compensation/ pay	JS2_6	0.548	0.294	Valid
	JS2_7	0.527	0.294	Valid
	JS2_8	0.571	0.294	Valid
	JS2_9	0.783	0.294	Valid
	JS2_10	0.746	0.294	Valid
Trust between employees and senior management	JS3_11	0.764	0.294	Valid
	JS3_12	0.544	0.294	Valid
	JS3_13	0.647	0.294	Valid
	JS3_14	0.534	0.294	Valid
	JS3_15	0.621	0.294	Valid
Job security	JS4_16	0.749	0.294	Valid
	JS4_17	0.687	0.294	Valid
	JS4_18	0.585	0.294	Valid
	JS4_19	0.721	0.294	Valid
	JS4_20	0.493	0.294	Valid
Opportunities to use skills and abilities	JS5_21	0.687	0.294	Valid
	JS5_22	0.571	0.294	Valid
	JS5_23	0.405	0.294	Valid
	JS5_24	0.436	0.294	Valid
	JS5_25	0.619	0.294	Valid
Leadership	EX1_26	0.823	0.294	Valid
	EX1_27	0.777	0.294	Valid
Teamwork	EX2_28	0.753	0.294	Valid
	EX2_29	0.741	0.294	Valid
Social Climate	EX3_30	0.741	0.294	Valid
	EX3_31	0.661	0.294	Valid
Work Organization	EX4_32	0.497	0.294	Valid
	EX4_33	0.695	0.294	Valid
	EX4_34	0.553	0.294	Valid
Work Control and Flexibility	EX5_35	0.650	0.294	Valid
Growth and Rewards	EX6_36	0.683	0.294	Valid
	EX6_37	0.624	0.294	Valid
Purpose	EX7_38	0.509	0.294	Valid
Technology	EX8_39	0.539	0.294	Valid
Physical Environment	EX9_40	0.724	0.294	Valid
Thoughts of Quitting	TI1_41	0.676	0.294	Valid
Intention to Quit	TI2_42	0.569	0.294	Valid
Intention to Look for Another job	TI3_43	0.458	0.294	Valid

Reliability Test

The reliability of each construct was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha. Results showed job satisfaction at 0.932, employee experience at 0.928, and turnover intention at 0.727. Based on Hair et al. (2010), these values indicate excellent to acceptable reliability, confirming that the questionnaire is internally consistent and appropriate for further analysis.

Table 4. Variable Reliability

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability Level
Job Satisfaction	25	0.932	Excellent
Employee Experience	15	0.928	Excellent
Turnover Intention	3	0.727	Acceptable

Descriptive Analysis

Summarizing across variables, job satisfaction scored 3.24 (Fair), employee experience 2.53 (Fair), and turnover intention 2.14 (Fair). High marks for respectful treatment and teamwork suggest positive relationships, but concerns exist around compensation, growth, and retention. These results address RQ1 by offering a comprehensive view of how employees perceive their work and workplace.

Table 5 Summary of Descriptive Results

Variable	Dimension	Score	Mean	Evaluation	Variable Score	Verdict
Job Satisfaction	Respectful treatment of all employees at all levels	769	3.42	Good	3.24	Fair
	Compensation/ pay	646	2.87	Fair		
	Trust between employees and senior management	765	3.40	Good		
	Job security	697	3.10	Fair		
	Opportunities to use skills and abilities	766	3.40	Good		
Employee Experience	Leadership	299	3.32	Good	2.53	Fair
	Teamwork	316	3.51	Good		
	Social Climate	320	3.56	Good		
	Work Organization	455	3.37	Good		
	Work Control and Flexibility	160	3.56	Good		
	Growth and Rewards	288	3.20	Fair		
	Purpose	143	3.18	Fair		
	Technology	146	3.24	Fair		
	Physical Environment	154	3.42	Good		
Turnover Intention	I often think about quitting my current job	85	1.89	Poor	2.14	Fair
	I plan to look for another job within the next 12 months	78	1.73	Very Poor		
	I intend to stay at this company for the next year	126	2.80	Fair		

Inferential Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis was used to examine the relationships among variables. Job satisfaction correlated negatively with turnover intention ($r = -0.482$), as did employee experience ($r = -0.404$), both significant at $p < 0.01$. Additionally, job satisfaction and employee experience had a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.838$), indicating a close connection between how employees feel about their work and their experience at the company.

Table 6. Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variable	Job Satisfaction	Employee Experience	Turnover Intention
Job Satisfaction	1		
Employee Experience	0.838**	1	
Turnover Intention	-0.482**	-0.404**	1

A multiple regression analysis assessed the influence of job satisfaction and employee experience on turnover intention. Assumption testing confirmed normality ($p = 0.200$), multicollinearity ($VIF < 5$), and independence of residuals.

The model summary showed $R = 0.482$ and $R^2 = 0.232$, meaning 23.2% of the variation in turnover intention can be explained by the two predictors. The ANOVA test confirmed model significance ($F = 6.344$, $p = 0.004$). Coefficient analysis revealed job satisfaction had a marginally significant negative effect ($B = -0.090$, $p = 0.059$), while employee experience was not significant ($B = -0.001$, $p = 0.994$).

Table 7. Kolmogorov–Smirnov Normality Test of Residuals

		Unstandardized Residual	
N		45	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0.0000000	
	Std. Deviation	1.70717702	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.088	
	Positive	0.088	
	Negative	-0.087	
Test Statistic		0.088	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c		.200 ^d	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^e	Sig.	0.509	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0.496
		Upper Bound	0.521

Table 8. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.482 ^a	.232	.195	1.747

Table 9. ANOVA Table

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	38.742	2	19.371	6.344	.004 ^b
Residual	128.236	42	3.053		
Total	166.978	44			

Table 10. Coefficients Table

Predictor	B	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	13.734	–	6.406	<.001
Job Satisfaction	-0.090	-0.480	-1.938	0.059
Employee Experience	-0.001	-0.002	-0.007	0.994

In conclusion, job satisfaction appears to influence turnover intention more strongly than employee experience in this context. These findings answer RQ2 by identifying job satisfaction as a key predictor.

Business Solution

The study identified that both job satisfaction and employee experience at PT XYZ were rated as "Fair," with turnover intention also falling into a "Fair" range—indicating a tangible retention risk. Correlation and regression analyses showed that both factors negatively influence turnover intention, with job satisfaction having a slightly stronger predictive power.

To address the identified gaps, eight key problem areas were mapped directly from low-scoring survey items. These include issues in conflict resolution, managerial communication, recognition, training support, compensation fairness, career clarity, resource availability, and technology enablement. Each area has been matched with actionable solutions, such as implementing transparent SOPs, launching competency-based training programs, revising the reward system, and upgrading digital tools.

These solutions are aimed at improving core employee experiences and strengthening retention by aligning organizational practices with employee expectations.

Implementation Strategy

The implementation strategy is structured across three timeframes, short-term (0–6 months), medium-term (6–18 months), and long-term (18+ months) to ensure change is both actionable and sustainable. Each solution is phased to align with organizational readiness and is anchored by measurable outcomes.

Table 11. Implementation Strategy

Item	Short Term	Medium Term	Long Term
Conflict Resolution Practices	Introduce SOPs for conflict resolution and rollout across departments.	Provide mediation training for managers to build resolution skills.	Integrate conflict metrics into HR dashboards and reviews.
Management Communication	Launch regular internal communication forums and newsletters.	Introduce feedback platforms and anonymous suggestion boxes.	Include communication training in leadership development programs.
Training & Development Support	Conduct training needs assessment and initiate pilot learning sessions.	Launch structured development programs based on competencies.	Establish a dedicated internal Learning Academy.
Rewards & Recognition	Promote informal recognition practices such as shout-outs and peer nominations.	Implement standardized performance-based incentive programs.	Embed recognition into company culture through strategic programs.
Resource Availability	Conduct audits to identify tool and resource gaps.	Introduce ticketing system for streamlined resource requests.	Include resource planning in annual strategic budgeting.
Compensation Transparency	Hold briefings on current pay structures and philosophies.	Benchmark salaries and establish formal pay bands.	Conduct regular compensation reviews and publish transparency reports.
Job Security & Career Clarity	Distribute organizational updates and FAQs to address concerns.	Initiate mentoring and career counseling programs.	Develop a career path framework with promotion criteria.
Technology Enablement	Resolve existing IT issues and stabilize critical systems.	Upgrade infrastructure and provide training on digital tools.	Implement a digital innovation roadmap for future alignment.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between job satisfaction, employee experience, and turnover intention at PT XYZ. Descriptive analysis showed that both job satisfaction (3.24) and employee experience (2.53) were rated as “Fair,” with notable weaknesses in

areas such as compensation, communication, recognition, and access to resources. These gaps reflect employee dissatisfaction that may contribute to higher turnover intention.

Inferential analysis confirmed that job satisfaction significantly and negatively affects turnover intention, while employee experience, though correlated, was not a significant predictor in the regression model. This suggests that while employee experience shapes general sentiment, job satisfaction plays a more direct role in influencing the intent to stay.

Based on these findings, PT XYZ is advised to prioritize initiatives that enhance job satisfaction, including fair compensation, transparent communication, recognition systems, and career development opportunities. Strengthening employee experience through improved technology, supportive leadership, and resource availability also remains important.

For future research, demographic variables such as age, tenure, and gender should be considered to explore their moderating effects. Longitudinal and mixed-method studies are also recommended to better capture employee perceptions over time and to evaluate the impact of implemented strategies.

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Cite this Article: Permana, A.D., Febriansyah, H. (2025). The Analysis of Job Satisfaction and Employee Experience on Turnover Intention in Telecommunication Service Companies. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(7), pp. 3551-3559. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i7-41>